

IPERION HS

CALL: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1

GA n. 871034

D.4.1 Title: MOLAB First Access Report

Lead Author: Costanza Miliani

Co-author: Brenda Doherty

Contributors: David Buti; Paraskevi Pouli; Vivi Tornari; Francesca Rosi; Aldo Romani; Paolo Romano; Giovanni Leucci; Nikos Papadopolous; Aurélie Tournie; Christine Andraud; Haida Liang; Piotr Targowski.

Document information

Project number	871034	Acronym	IPERION HS
Full title	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science		
Project url	www.iperionhs.eu		
EU Project Officer	Maria Theofilatou		

Deliverable	Number	D.4.1	Title	MOLAB First Access Report
Work Package	Number	WP. 4 TNA3	Title	MOLAB: access to mobile laboratories

Deliverable nature	<input type="checkbox"/> prototype <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> report <input type="checkbox"/> demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> other		
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential <input type="checkbox"/> Restricted		
Contractual delivery date	(30/06/2022)		
Actual delivery date	(11/07/2022)		
Status	Version 0.0	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final	

Authors (Partner)				
Responsible Author	Name	Costanza Miliani	Email	Costanza.miliani@cnr.it
	Partner	CNR-ISPC	Phone	+39 3470323817

Total number of pages	--
Keywords	

Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. no.	Author	Change
29/06/2022	0.1	C. Milani	Updates to 4 th Call selection
07/07/2022	0.2	C. Miliani	Updates to access

Abstract

(300-500 words)

This deliverable documents the organization and implementation of procedures, functioning, findings, and results developed during the period M1-27 of WP4 MOLAB: access to mobile laboratories. Where the COVID-19 pandemic heavily influenced access provision being executed for travel limitations much effort was placed on establishing and implementing an integrated set of procedures within the entire IPERION HS Transnational Access (TNA) program also comprising the ARCHLAB (WP2) and FIXLAB (WP3) platforms as overseen and secured by the Central Activities of WP8 (T8.1).

Information herein is given regarding the largely automated practical operation yet with specific regards to the MOLAB Calls, from the website's catalogue of services, the online application of proposals and dashboard to the operations and functioning of the helpdesk (T4.1). Efforts relative to the steps involved in the selection process by which proposed projects submitted during this period were evaluated, selected and executed are importantly outlined (T4.2). The outreach of MOLAB and its activities (T4.3) during this period are outlined as too are the all too important aspects for data management (T4.4).

Finally, for the different facilities that compose the MOLAB platform, the activities of each access provider and the effective use of the MOLAB platform, including projects implemented, days of access, objectives of the work and results achieved are herein reported.

Table of contents

INTRODUCTION.....7

1. SECTION: STARTING WORK.....8

1.1. The Userhelpdesk.....8

1.2. The MOLAB providers in the automatic dashboard.....9

1.3. The MOLAB Peer Review Panel (M-PRP)10

1.4. On-line Application Form.....11

1.5. User Satisfaction Survey/Questionnaire 11

1.6. Calls for Proposals distribution measures..... 12

1.7. Flyer and Poster..... 12

1.8. Participated Events and publications..... 13

2. SECTION: MOLAB ACCESS ACTIVITIES (to M27) 16

2.1. Accessible Techniques..... 16

2.2. MOLAB Data Management 18

2.3. Calls of Proposals (January 2021-June 2022) 18

2.4. Process Selection Steps..... 18

2.5. Outline of MOLAB Peer Review Panel Activity..... 18

2.6. Transnational Access: Executed Projects and KPIs..... 22

2.6.1. Scientific Output of Executed Projects..... 23

3. CONCLUSIONS.....30

APPENDICES..... 31

Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
COVID-19	Corona Virus Disease 2019 (an infectious pandemic affecting Europe and most of the World at the time of writing that drastically reduced travelling and direct personal contact)
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science (this Project)
ERIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package
SC	Steering Committee
Mx.	Month N. X after project start
TNA	Transnational Access
M-PRP	MOLAB Peer Review Panel
PM	Person-Months per Participant

Narrative (technical) description

INTRODUCTION

The European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) is set to constitute a distributed infrastructure of partnering facilities of recognized excellence. These facilities as national partners within E-RIHS will offer access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, data, and specialized knowledge for advancing science and technologies in the field of heritage science. The TNA program in IPERION HS aims to integrate existing procedures towards the upcoming implementation and successive operation phases of E-RIHS ERIC.

To this end, the TNA program within the core of IPERION HS offers a vast portfolio of services and activities centred on the needs of the heritage science community in Europe and Associated Countries. The combined activity promotes the development of advanced research in the examination and conservation of works of art, offering users the access to unique European resources for in situ and laboratory investigations on artwork materials through three TNA platforms: ARCHLAB (WP2), FIXLAB (WP3) and MOLAB (WP4). Through these three programs of access, there is the objective to deliver to users (from novice to experienced users) not only experimental resources but also methodological approaches, compliant best practices, tools and technologies to permit them to carry out their research projects in conditions otherwise impossible for them. The automation of services in IPERION HS means that the TNA program is managed as three unique platforms by respective Coordinators which are connected and respectively integrated.

The Mobile LABORatory, MOLAB, in IPERION HS (<https://www.iperionhs.eu/molab/>), consists of key laboratories wide-stretching in 10 European and UK countries. It provides coherent access, under a unified management structure, to an extensive set of state-of-the-art portable equipment and related competences, for in-situ non-invasive measurements of artworks, collections, monuments and sites. Measurements are carried out in the same location where the actual artwork under examination is located or exhibited, i.e., museum, restoration workshop, on scaffold, archaeological site etc.

MOLAB presents specific TNA qualities, in that:

- the user does not move to the infrastructure, but it is the instrumentation that moves to the site where the user is working.
- a toolbox of 38 different high-performance and well-integrated portable experimental techniques (ranging from point analysis, 2D/3D analyses, multi/hyperspectral imaging and mapping and remote sensing) is available together with fully trained operators.
- the operators a) assemble the various instrumentation/s *in-situ*; b) carry out the measurements in direct collaboration with the User, c) aid interpretation and discuss the results with the users.

1. STARTING WORK

Main objectives of the first 27 months have seen the launch of MOLAB program among potential users and the effective starting and running of the program. As mentioned in MOLAB's periodic technical report, access commenced at M18.

This unavoidable delay worked to the advantage of the TNA program, where the effort of WP8 in implementing an online automatic system "the IPERION HS dashboard" is praised together with the full collaboration of WP2, WP3 and WP4 Coordinators. This achievement consists in each step of access being online- from the offer detailed in a specifically constructed catalogue of services and online submission of applications and outcome of selection processes, to the archiving of a project following access. This has greatly improved and facilitated the entire access experience for the platforms, the providers and the users alike.

Herein we report a series of progressive activities, reported in depth below, that have been planned and carried out. The assistance of potential Users, project optimizations and any general information is relayed to the fully functional MOLAB Helpdesk from the overseeing UserHelpdesk. All responsible MOLAB providers have received instruction as to the newly implemented dashboard and its internal functioning for the project feasibility assessment and the closing of successful proposals following access provision. The MOLAB peer review panel (M-PRP) has been appointed and oversees assessing proposals submitted to each call according to a set of criteria implemented for the TNA program. Effort regarding the diffusion of information on the opportunities offered by the MOLAB access programme, giving maximum publicity to the advantages, innovations, and related improvements, through constructed web pages on TNA implementation, and production of a MOLAB poster and flyer are all reported. Subsequently, the starting of the access activities, the opening of calls for proposals with a five-month cadence, the evaluation and rank of the users' projects within M27 from Calls 1-4; the implementation of relative first, second and third call access projects where possible; the publication of Users' Reports on the project website and the feedback through the User Satisfaction form are all considered. Highlights of the presentations of the activities at conferences and webinars oriented to users, and diffusion through media for the involvement of the public are all then mentioned. The interaction of specific WPs and sub-tasks will be mentioned where relevant

1.1. The UserHelpdesk

The UserHelpdesk, with single entry point userhelpdesk@iperionhs.eu provides an integrated and much relevant user welcoming and support service for the complete TNA program which is open for the duration of the entire project. The active desk responds to any general user query or requests by e-mail and forwards to the individual platforms for technical information, potential risks and logistics. The MOLAB Helpdesk, molab.iperionhs@ispc.cnr.it can reiterate orientation towards specific experimental set-ups through the catalogue of services which has been constructed and is available online for each of the techniques offered for TNA. The desk can offer support to potential MOLAB users in the proposal preparation to permit for a most profitable investigation campaign planning.

The UserHelpdesk can also oversee the dashboard and be of technical assistance for the user, providers and coordinators alike.

1.2. The MOLAB Providers in the automatic dashboard

The 19 MOLAB providers (table 1) are current representatives of their facility and specific techniques offered in IPERION HS. They have received interactive dashboard demonstrations tailored for MOLAB (23rd & 27th November 2020) and have received the short guidelines as constructed by CO in WP8 (see inset). They are in receipt of any activity within the internal automated dashboard requesting their MOLAB instrumentation. These providers oversee the technical assessment of each individual project proposal submitted at each call. Their e-mail contacts are also visible in the online catalogue of services should a potential user contact them directly. The time frame for technical feasibility is set to 2 weeks following the call deadline. Each proposal can be deemed technically “feasible” or “unfeasible” and specific comments relating to scientific interest in the project are gathered. Important questions regarding specific logistics are made at this stage and are communicated to the proposer via the UserHelpdesk who has vision of the entire TNA platforms feasibility along with the corresponding Coordinators. All feasible projects are then passed to the MOLAB Peer Review Panel (M-PRP). On finalizing the selection at each call, the representative providers are informed of projects awarded access. Following the access campaign, the responsible provider closes the project in the dashboard.

Table 1: List of the MOLAB provider representatives

Installation		
ID/No.	Short name	Dashboard Responsible
MOLAB.it	CNR-SCITEC (UNIPG)	Francesca Rosi (Aldo Romani)
	CNR-ISPC _a	Francesco Paolo Romano
	CNR-ISPC _b	Nicola Masini
	CNR-ISPC _c	Giovanni Leucci
	CNR-INO	Raffaella Fontana
MOLAB.fr	CNRS-C2RMF	Vincent Detalle
	(LRMF)	David Giovanacci
	(MNHN)	Christina Andraud
MOLAB.pl	NCU	Piotr Targowski
MOLAB.gr	FORTH-IESL	Vivi Tornari
	FORTH-IMS	Apostolos Saris updated 10th June 2022 with: Nikos Papadopolous

	FORTH-Of ADC	Georgios Karagiannis
MOLAB.pt	UEVORA	António Candeias
MOLAB.es	CSIC	Emilio Cano
MOLAB.de	SPK-RWTH	Alina Adams
MOLAB.ro	INOE	Roxan Radavan
MOLAB.cy	CYI	Sorin Hermon
MOLAB.uk	UCL-NTU	Haida Liang

1.3. The MOLAB Peer Review Panel (M-PRP)

The **Peer Review Panels (PRP)**, one representing each platform, are composed of acknowledged experts selected outside the consortium and are in charge of the scientific evaluation, scoring and ranking of all TNA feasible submissions. For MOLAB, the organization of the Peer Review Panel foresees four members, external to the consortium, individually recognised for their expertise on applications to the ample fields of non-invasive analyses of cultural heritage. This scientific panel

Evaluation criteria
35% Scientific excellence
25% Assessment of the state of the art of the topic and advancements in the field
20% Valorisation and dissemination plan
15% Expertise of User Group
5% Potential impact

oversees evaluating the users group proposals based on common weighted peer review criterions (see inset), ranking them and selecting those most appropriate and scientifically sound. Contacts were established by the WP4 Coordinator and the MOLAB providers with interested and eminent external members. The MOLAB Peer Review Panel (MOLAB PRP), as proposed by

MOLAB and appointed by the project Steering Committee is composed of: *Dr. Alison Heritage*-Conservation Research Specialist, ICCROM, Italy. *Dr. Marc Walton*- Head, Conservation and Research at M+ Museum for Visual Culture, Hong Kong. *Dr. Elsa Bourguignon*: Head of Research Lab Unit at Louvre Abu Dhabi and *Dr. Arianna Traviglia*- Coordinator of the Centre for Cultural Heritage Technology, IIT, Venice, Italy.

IPERION HS introduces an innovation in the reviewing process through the use of additional experts in a common PRP basket. Briefly the TNA WP coordinators can call on additional experts, when and if necessary, to involve them in the evaluation of the proposals, as related to their specific experience. Details of this basket of experts is held in a list in accordance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) from which the TNA coordinators can select the desired reviewers.

1.4. On-line Application Form

The *Application Form* which is filled out by the User group leader is submitted exclusively online following registration. The live template and downloadable project description are representative of the TNA program, following the addition of instruments being selected from the online catalogue of services. The application form is tailored for the specifics of MOLAB users: with sections requesting a concise presentation of the proposed research project, with a clear indication of the objectives and expected results; the foreseen duration of the access and the desired period; a clear explanation of why a mobile facility is necessary to carry out the measurements, as well as a description of the site and accessibility of the subject of the measurements. The consent of the owner/s of the artwork to be investigated and any permissions for done equipment and advice for Users to pre-determine any national radiation protection measures (licenses/accreditations) for visiting MOLAB X-ray based instrumentations is suggested. There is also a mandatory final section outlined in the application form, outlining the duties of the Users should their project be selected for MOLAB TNA. Specifically, the User must provide a User Report (image inset) and fill out the User satisfaction survey form relative to the platform no later than 2 months after MOLAB Access. That the results which are obtained in connection with any MOLAB activity related to the present proposal, are intended to be published in accordance with the IPERION HS Access Policy and that the support by the EU will be acknowledged in any such published material using the statement *"Financial support by the Access to Research Infrastructures activity in the H2020 Programme of the EU (IPERION HS Grant Agreement n. 871034) is gratefully acknowledged"* and adding the EU flag in a relevant position.

1.5. User Satisfaction Survey/Questionnaire

In line with the IPERION HS access quality system and for a continued improvement in MOLAB’s access provision, all User Group leaders, are requested by automatic e-mail from the dashboard system after access completion, to complete an evaluation questionnaire. This survey has been prepared in collaboration with the MOLAB representative of sub-task T4.3 (monitoring and evaluation- outreach) and the Quality Manager/officer in T1.3 and T8.1. It is homogenized and integrated across the three TNA platforms. It is composed of a series of questions to be answered on inserting a rating from 1 (very poor) to 10 (excellent) regarding- publicity of the services; support from the UserHelpdesk; communication, interaction and collaboration with the providers at each step of the access from planning to execution; overall indication of the value of the results obtained for the advancement of the research. A further free text field permits suggestions to be formulated regarding any aspect of the TNA services which can be shared internally within the platform. The survey is carried out online

1.8. Participated events and publications

Information on transnational access and performances of the MOLAB facilities, has been also diffused through presentations in this period within online/ in-presence international conferences or workshops and through publications within the international scientific literature. A compiled list of presentations at conferences and workshops (invited lectures and oral or poster communications) typically attended by researchers in the field of Heritage Science are reported where MOLAB has been presented and had a clear visibility:

- SPIE Optical Metrology symposium, Optics for Arts, Architecture and Archaeology (O3A) Conference 21-25th June 2021, Various members of ISAAC group gave talks that mentioned IPERION HS MOLAB (MOLAB.uk)
- Cambridge University Festival, March 2021 spectral imaging and manuscripts (MOLAB.uk Haida Liang).
- Shandong University, China, April 2021 remote imaging, machine learning and wall paintings on the Silk Road (MOLAB.uk Haida Liang).
- Yale University Institute for the Preservation of Cultural Heritage, May 2021 AI for processing large scale spectral imaging datasets (MOLAB.uk Haida Liang).
- ICOM-CC May 2021, presentation on Remote multimodal laser spectroscopy for wall paintings by Yu Li (MOLAB.uk Haida Liang).
- IPERION HS Doctoral Summer School July 2021: Optical Coherence Tomography for planning and monitoring of conservation of paintings (MOLAB.pl Piotr Targowski & Magdalena Iwanicka)
- IPERION HS Doctoral Summer School July 2021 In-situ electrochemical impedance spectroscopy for the study of metallic cultural heritage (MOLAB.es Emilio Cano)
- IPERION HS Doctoral Summer School July 2021 Spectral imaging and machine learning aided data processing for history and conservation research (MOLAB.uk Haida Liang)
- IPERION HS Doctoral Summer School July 2021 Unveiling the composition of historical plastics through non-invasive reflection FT-IR spectroscopy in the extended near- and mid-Infrared spectral range (MOLAB.it Francesca Rosi)
- Science and Technology for Cultural Heritage, a Nature Italy event, 18th November 2021 (MOLAB.it Costanza Miliani (Invited lecture)).
- Smart NanoMaterials (SNAIA) conference, December 2021, remote standoff imaging and spectroscopy of wall paintings, (MOLAB.uk Haida Liang (invited talk)).
- ARTICT (Computational approaches for technical imaging in cultural heritage) conference organised by the National Gallery, UCL, Imperial and Duke Universities, April 2022 “New developments on simultaneous MA-XRD/MA-XRF imaging: instrumental setup and computational approaches for pigment-specific mapping of paintings” Francesco Paolo Romano, Costanza Miliani, Claudia Caliri, Claudia Fatuzzo, Danilo Pavone, Giulia Privitera, Dario Zappalà & Zdenek Preisler

- ARTICT (Computational approaches for technical imaging in cultural heritage) conference organised by the National Gallery, UCL, Imperial and Duke Universities, April 2022, AI for DigiLab (MOLAB.uk Haida Liang (invited talk)).
- International symposium, Crossroads June 2022, Data-driven talks on ancient materiality at the interface of archaeology, science and engineering organised by MIT and the Egyptian Museum in Turin. (MOLAB.uk Haida Liang (invited lecture)).
- International symposium, Crossroads June 2022, Data-driven talks on ancient materiality at the interface of archaeology, science and engineering organised by MIT and the Egyptian Museum in Turin. (MOLAB.it Costanza Miliani (invited lecture)).
- 2020 IMEKO TC-4 International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage Trento, Italy, October 22-24, 2020 (MOLAB.it CNR-ISPC_c Giovanni Leucci).
- 2021 IMEKO TC-4 International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage Milano, Italy, October 22-24, 2021 (MOLAB.it CNR-ISPC_c Giovanni Leucci).
- Corso di Diagnostica per il Restauro, Dipartimento di Scienze e Ingegneria della materia, dell’Ambiente ed Urbanistica, Università politecnica delle Marche – December 2020. Title: Attraverso le sfumature del tempo - Dall'arte Pre-Colombiana a quella Contemporanea: approccio spettroscopico integrato per lo studio dei materiali pittorici e del loro degrado (MOLAB.it CNR-ISPC David Buti)
- Advanced Training Course, Sudan INNOVATION - A new Sudan through culture, technology and innovation – February 2021. Title: Understanding, documenting and sharing the materiality of Ancient Manuscripts (MOLAB.it CNR-ISPC David Buti)
- Seminario Scuola di Dottorato di ricerca in Patrimoni archeologici, storici, architettonici e paesaggistici mediterranei: sistemi integrati di conoscenza, progettazione, tutela e valorizzazione (PASAP Med) – aprile 2022 Title: European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science: Opportunità di accesso a laboratori e strumentazioni all'avanguardia per la conoscenza e l'innovazione nel campo delle scienze del patrimonio culturale (MOLAB.it CNR-ISPC David Buti).
- International School of Cultural Heritage June 2022 – Technologies for Archeology, Digital and Technologies for Archaeology: Environments and Tools (MOLAB.it Costanza Miliani)

MOLAB in collaboration with WP7 and WP8 have also participated in the HS Academy webinar series providing a key source of updated information on MOLABs’ heritage science facilities and access program. The webinars have had the capacity to reach a wide audience in the interdisciplinary fields by showcasing highlights of access campaigns (investigation of Islamic manuscripts) and instrumentation capabilities (Imaging techniques and remote sensing) as well as the application of MOLAB within the field of built heritage and archaeology.

Press Releases

The MOLAB action in the project GRANJA (2nd Call) appeared in the newspaper El Adelantado (13/02/2022). It can be consulted <https://www.eladelantado.com/provincia-de-segovia/expertos-analizan-las-primeras-piezas-de-la-real-fabricade-cristales-de-la-granja/>

Publications of scientific literature during the period to M27 include:

- Comisi F., De Giorgi L., **Leucci G.**, Integrated use of GPR and TDR for wood permittivity evaluation. Proceedings 2020 IMEKO TC-4 International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage Trento, Italy, October 22-24, 2020- ISBN: 978-92-990084-9-2. pp 1-4
- De Giorgi L., **Leucci G.**, A new methodological approach on the evaluation of stability of cavities in "soft" carbonate rocks. Proceedings 2020 IMEKO TC-4 International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage Trento, Italy, October 22-24, 2020- ISBN: 978-92-990084-9-2. pp 133-135
- De Giorgi L., De Pascalis G., Ferrari I., Giuri F., **Leucci G.**, 2020. 3D GPR and ERT surveys at the coastal tower of S. Caterina (Lecce, Italy). Proceedings 2020 IMEKO TC-4 International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage Trento, Italy, October 22-24, 2020- ISBN: 978-92-990084-9-2. pp 136-139;
- Doherty, B.; Degano, I.; Romani, A.; Higgitt, C.; Peggie, D.; Colombini, M.P.; Miliani, C. Identifying Brazilwood’s Marker Component, Urolithin C, in Historical Textiles by Surface-

Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy. *Heritage* **2021**, *4*, 1415-1428.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage4030078>.

- La Nasa, J., Doherty, B., Rosi, F. *et al.* An integrated analytical study of crayons from the original art materials collection of the MUNCH museum in Oslo. *Sci Rep* **2021**, *11*, 7152. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-86031-6>.
- Monico, L., Rosi, F., Vivani, R., Cartechini, L., Janssens, K., Gauquelin, N., ... & Romani, A. Deeper insights into the photoluminescence properties and (photo) chemical reactivity of cadmium red (CdS_{1-x}Se_x) paints in renowned twentieth century paintings by state-of-the-art investigations at multiple length scales. *The European Physical Journal Plus*, **2022**, *137*(3), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjp/s13360-022-02447-7>
- Carrozzo A. R., De Giorgi L., **Leucci G.**, Longhitano L. 2022. Non-destructive diagnosis of a hypogean mill. *Journal of physics. Conference series* [10.1088/1742-6596/2204/1/012002](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2204/1/012002)
- Tanasi D., Hassam S., Trapani P., Cali D., De Giorgi L., Ferrari I., Giuri G., **Leucci G.** 2022. Preliminary results from GPR survey at the Roman villa of Caddeddi (Siracusa, Italy). *Journal of physics. Conference series* [10.1088/1742-6596/2204/1/012006](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2204/1/012006)

2. MOLAB ACCESS ACTIVITIES (to 27)

2.1. Accessible techniques

During this period the collection of MOLAB movable instruments (table 2) have been offered by the partnership of ten providing countries with instrumentation from 19 laboratories to the selected users, in order to permit access campaigns to be carried out with no sampling and no contact on artworks, monuments or sites.

Table 2: List of the MOLAB equipment per providing laboratory

Installation		Techniques provided within MOLAB
ID/No.	Short name	
MOLAB.it	CNR-SCITEC (UNIPG)	1 Total reflection mid/near-FTIR; Raman (λ_{exc} 785 & 1064nm) 2 Raman (λ_{exc} 532nm); Macro XRF mapping; X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) 3 high resolution digital microscopy; (UV-VIS-NIR reflectance 4 UV-VIS fluorescence; UV-VIS fluorescence time-decay 5 Reflection VIS hyperspectral imaging (400-900 nm) 6 UV-Vis induced fluorescence hyperspectral imaging (400-900 nm))
	CNR-ISPC@CT	7 PIXE/ low energy XRF 8 Confocal XRF mapping 9 Micro-XRF mapping; 10 XRD mapping
	CNR-ISPC@PZ	11 Aerial remote sensing (UAV - RGB+Multispectral imagery) 12 Aerial remote sensing (UAV - IRT imagery) 13 Aerial remote sensing (LiDAR)
	CNR-ISPC@LE	14 Fluxgate gradiometry,

		15 Ground Penetrating Radar - medium and high frequency antenna
	CNR-INO	16 Scanning multispectral VIS-NIR reflectography; 17 Optical profilometry
MOLAB.fr	CNRS(C2RMF)	18 Hyphenate XRD/XRF; 19 Hyphenate LIBS/LIF/Raman; 20 NIR hyperspectral imaging (900-2500 nm)
	(LRMF)	21 Terahertz imaging; 22 Thermography
	(MNHN)	23 NIR hyperspectral imaging (900-2500 nm)
MOLAB.pl	NCU	24 Optical Coherence Tomography (1960 nm)
MOLAB.gr	FORTH-IESL	25 Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry (DHSPI)
	FORTH-IMS	26 Laser scanning, total station and GPS; 27 Electrical Resistivity Tomography; 28 soil resistivity and conductivity techniques; 29 magnetic susceptibility measurements
	FORTH-Of ADC	30 Acoustic tomography
MOLAB.pt	UEVORA	31 Cytometer, 32 DNA and RNA sequencer, 33 luminometer lumitester, 34 PCR and electrophoresis system
MOLAB.es	CSIC	35 Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy
MOLAB.de	SPK-RWTH	36 NMR depth-profiling/relaxometry
MOLAB.ro	INOE	37 UAV Photogrammetry; 38 3D structure-light scanner and 3D laser scanners
MOLAB.cy	CYI	39 Imaging methods for non-invasive dendrochronology 40 3D modelling
MOLAB.uk	UCL-NTU	41 Remote VIS/NIR spectral imaging for rapid survey of large areas; 42 Remote Vis/NIR/SWIR hyperspectral imaging; 43 Remote Raman/LIF/LIBS spectroscopy; 44 Optical Coherence Tomography (800 nm)

2.2. MOLAB Data Management

The work undertaken in task 4.4 with the collaboration of MOLAB providers (CNR/SCITEC/UNIPG/ISPC, CYI, CNRS, FORTH, HERCULES, INOE, UCL/NTU-ISAAC/NG)

has concentrated on the standardisation of data documentation and curation produced during the MOLAB access program. The purpose of this was to foster cooperation and effective exchange of results and conclusions among MOLAB providers involved in the same access project, to provide the user (beneficiary) with results in structurally unified documents, and to move towards openly accessed searchable database of results (as expected by DIGILAB) for effective data and results reuse after the completion of the IPERION HS project.

In cooperation with WP 5, work is underway on the final solution, fully compliant with the Data Management Plan. However, taking advantage of the delayed start of access activities caused by the pandemic, an intermediate solution in the form of a structured report template was developed and implemented before the start of access provision. The document has been prepared as an editable text in two versions: for mobile objects and heritage sites. Using previous results of the PARTHENOS project and discussions with experienced providers, the HML compliant structure was proposed and tested on results from E-RIHS.it MOLAB activity. The concept includes the significant User involvement at the stage of preparation of the access: she or he is asked to provide comprehensive information on the object/site, which providers can use to prepare the access properly. This information is included in the report as a separate part. The report also comprises the description of the methodology used, technical data of the instrument as well as the conditions of the examination. Then the results are given together with conclusions. This way, the report constitutes a complete document, searchable by metadata and providing comprehensive information about conducted examination. During the implementation phase, comments from users and providers are collected and minor corrections to the documents are made.

MOLAB Transnational Access programme within the EU H2020 Project IPERION HS, contract no. 871034.

MOLAB Transnational Access Report

..... [Date of preparation]
[fill in the dots and replace (green text)]
[delete all (comments in blue and italic) after filling in]

Call

Project Title:

Acronym:

User Leader (Name):

MOLAB Provider(s):[institution]

Access dates on site and place of examination:

Access provided by: [give names (and affiliations - if different to MOLAB provider) of all persons involved in the access]

Report prepared by: [give names here]

with Object descriptions provided by: [give names here]

(City of preparation of the report, Country abbreviation, year of preparation)

2.3. Call of proposals (January 2021- June 2022)

In accordance with the adjusted schedule, four calls of proposals have been published under the MOLAB TNA programme, with the following deadlines:

-31st January 2021 (first call),

-30th June 2021 (second call),

-30th November 2021 (third call),

-29th April 2022 (fourth call).

2.4. Process steps

Due to the multi-faced accessible experimental techniques, the entire evaluation and assessment of proposals incorporates the following steps:

Step 1 – Information

As reported above, necessary information is provided on the IPERION HS website, through the TNA UserHelpdesk services which passes to the MOLAB helpdesk and on direct contact with the facility provider. For application optimization, potential users are invited to request technical and scientific advice where applicable

Step 2 – Submission

Proposers submitted their proposal through the single online entry point (using the MOLAB Application form once registered on the website), selecting the specific experimental set-up of interest from the catalogue of services.

Step 3 – MOLAB providers technical feasibility assessment

Following the deadline of each Call, providers supply an initial assessment of only each individual project submitted requesting their specific facility and techniques. Each proposal on the dashboard is deemed technically feasible or unfeasible where requested experimental techniques are considered appropriate or not, together with specific comments relating to scientific interest in the project. Important questions regarding specific logistics are made and communicated to the proposer.

Step 4 – Peer-Review Evaluation

Applications are then transferred to the *Peer Review Panel* in order to evaluate the scientific content of the project and rank the proposals according to implemented TNA ranking guidelines

The selection is based on the project *scientific quality*, following the principles of transparency, fairness and impartiality according to the sum of a weighted multi-criterion analysis. Specific criteria include: 1/scientific excellence, 2/*Assessment of the state of the art of the topic and of the advancements of the field*, 3/*valorization and dissemination plan* 4/*expertise of user group*, 5/*Potential impact* as well as 6/*dissemination plan*.

Step 5 – Final decision

The results of the M-PRP assessment are reported and discussed during each M-PRP meeting chaired by WP4 Coordinator, Costanza Miliani and in attendance also with the MOLAB representative T4.2 (Access provision management). Each meeting is finalized with the agreed listing of selected successful projects, projects to be strengthened and re-submitted and unsuccessful projects. Applicants are duly notified on insertion of results into the dashboard by automatic e-mail. Conclusions of the Peer Review process together with specific comments can be given to the user group leader on reasonable request to the helpdesk.

Step 6 – Timing and access modality

Access is allocated regarding according to availability of the instrument in the requested period and any specific User needs. For each access campaign, a MOLAB team leader is identified by T4.2 who has the role to contact the Users Group Leader and plan the modality and extent of the access in accordance with each provider (days, period, logistics etc.). The MOLAB unit of access is defined per day. The work to be developed includes: (i) preparatory work, (ii) transport of the equipment to site, (iii) use of portable equipment and (iv) preliminary processing/interpretation of the acquired data. Each project will be of variable duration depending on the nature and complexity of the specific research under study. Typically, each on-site intervention is expected to last maximum 5 days per provider.

Step 7 – Users duties

Each User Group Leader is ultimately reminded via an automatic e-mail from the dashboard on access completion to complete and upload the User Report on his/her MOLAB access' experiments

within 2 months following MOLAB TNA access. Excerpts of the MOLAB User Reports are published in the IPERION website.

2.5. Outline of MOLAB Peer Review Panel activity

1st Peer Review Panel Meeting

The first M-PRP meeting was held virtually on 25th March 2021 (15-16:20 CET). The following PRP members were present: Alison Heritage, Elsa Bourguignon and Arianna Traviglia. Apologies were sent by Marc Walton who sent the scores via e-mail prior to the meeting. The meeting was chaired by the WP4 Coordinator, Costanza Miliani. A report of the minutes was compiled containing the results of the assessment and a copy was distributed by e-mail and signed for the final approval of all the PRP members.

At the first call, 10 proposals (Appendix I for list) were received from Spain [4], Israel [1], Greece [1], Croatia [1], Czech Republic [1], Norway [1] and Italy [1]. Following the feasibility assessment by the requested MOLAB providers, 10 feasible proposals were passed to the M-PRP for evaluation.

Of these applications, 4 proposals were accepted for MOLAB TNA (NIBOTRAP, CH-MPPM and MRSL and PYRITEDINOSAUR), corresponding to a total of 10 access campaigns to be carried out by MOLAB.gr [1], MOLAB.it [SCITEC-2; INO-1; UNIPG-2], MOLAB.fr [2], MOLAB.uk [1], MOLAB.cy [1].

The applicants of the successful projects were notified by the dashboard. 3 further highly rating projects were advised to re-submit at the next Call and to contact the helpdesk for ulterior comments from the PRP and 3 projects were communicated to as being unsuccessful. See Table 3 for summary/appendix II for details.

2nd Peer Review Panel meeting

The second PRP meeting was held virtually on 6th September 2021 (15-16 CET). The following PRP members were present: Alison Heritage, Elsa Bourguignon and Arianna Traviglia. The temporary M-PRP member Clara Granzotto sent apologies and communicated her scores by e-mail. The meeting was chaired by the WP4 Coordinator, Costanza Miliani. A report of the minutes was compiled containing the results of this assessment and a copy was distributed by e-mail and signed for the final approval of all the PRP members.

At this call, 7 proposals (Appendix I for list) were received and all were considered feasible by the involved MOLAB providers. Applications were from User Group Leaders of 5 different countries: Ireland [1], Switzerland [1], Italy [2], Germany [1] and Spain [2]

In this meeting 3 proposals were selected for MOLAB TNA, (SuBaiae, DIACOMM and GRANJA). Accordingly, this was 11 access campaigns for MOLAB.gr [IESL-1; OF-ADC-1; IMS-1], MOLAB.fr [1], MOLAB.it [ISPC_a-2; ISPC_c-1; SCITEC-1; UNIPG-1], MOLAB.uk [1], MOLAB.de[1]

The applicants of the successful projects were notified via the dashboard's automatic e-mail. The remaining 4 projects were invited to re-submit at the next Call together with specific comments available on request from the helpdesk. See Table 3 for summary/appendix II for details.

3rd Peer Review Panel

The third PRP meeting was held virtually on 1st February 2022, (14-15:30 CET). The following PRP members were present: Alison Heritage, Elsa Bourguignon and Arianna Traviglia. A follow-up discussion was had with Marc Walton on 1st February 2022, (12-12:30 CET) and the meeting was chaired by the WP4 Leader, Costanza Miliani. A report of the minutes was compiled containing the

results of this assessment and a copy was distributed by e-mail and signed for the final approval of all the PRP members.

For this call, 13 proposals were received from User Group Leaders of 9 different countries: Ireland [1], Spain [3], Switzerland [2], France [1], Germany [1], Greece [1], Netherlands [1], Belgium [1] and Sweden [2]. Following the feasibility assessment by the MOLAB providers, 13 feasible proposals (Appendix 1 for list) were passed to the M-PRP for evaluation. Here, 3 proposals were selected for MOLAB TNA, (EPHA, HFTV-ReVis and BelMod) corresponds to 16 access campaigns for MOLAB.it [SCITEC-3, UNIPG-2, ISPC_a-3], MOLAB.pl [2], MOLAB.uk [2], MOLAB.es [1], MOLAB.fr [2] and MOLAB.gr [1]

The applicants of the successful and 10 unsuccessful-invited to resubmit projects were notified via e-mail from the dashboard. See Table 3 for summary/appendix II for details.

4th Peer Review Panel

The fourth PRP meeting was very recently held virtually on 29th June 2022, (10am Rome time). The following PRP members were present: Alison Heritage, Elsa Bourguignon and Arianna Traviglia and the meeting chaired by the WP4 vice Brenda Doherty. A report of the minutes is being compiled containing the results of this assessment and a copy is to be distributed by e-mail and signed for the final approval of all the PRP members.

At this call, 13 proposals were received from User Group Leaders of 9 different countries Switzerland [1], Greece [1], Netherlands [1], Croatia [2] and Sweden [2], Italy [1], UK [3], Norway [1] and Switzerland [1]. Following the feasibility assessment by the MOLAB providers, 11 feasible proposals (Appendix 1 for list) were passed to the M-PRP for evaluation, 4 of which were selected for access (Giotto@Bardi, MoMNopSaF, SIM and Synthetic Varnishes). A further 3 are to be invited to resubmit and the remaining 4 projects are unsuccessful. See Table 3 for summary/appendix II for details

Table 3 - Summary of the selection activities during the reporting period to M27 (MOLAB PRP)

Call (deadline)	Date of M-PRP Virtual Meeting	No. of <i>feasible</i> Proposals evaluated	Countries	Overview of evaluation of proposals
1st Call (31 st January 2021)	1 st M-PRP meeting: 25 th March 2021 15-16:20 CET	10	ES (x4), IL, HR, NO, CZ, IT, GR	4 successful_Selected for Access 3 invited to re-submit 3 unsuccessful_not selected for Access
2nd Call (30 th June 2021)	2 nd M-PRP meeting: 6 th September 2021 15-16 CET	7	IE, CH, IT (x2), DE, ES (x2)	3 successful_Selected for Access 4 invited to re-submit
3rd Call (30 th November 2021)	3 rd M-PRP meeting: 1 st February 2022 14- 15.30 CET	13	IE, CH (x2), NL, GR, ES (x3), SE (x2), DE, BE, FR	6 successful_Selected for Access, 2 of which pending 6 unsuccessful_not selected for Access
4th Call (29 th April 2022)	4 th M-PRP meeting: 20 th June 2022 11- 12 CET	11	NL, GR, SE (x2), IT, CH, UK (x3), NO, HR (x2), CZ	4 successful_Selected for Access 3 invited to re-submit 4 unsuccessful_not selected for Access

2.6. Transnational Access: Executed projects and KPIs

In the following, the projects implemented during from M18-M27 by the MOLAB providers are shortly described. The description includes the work developed, the days of access by each partner, the objectives of the measurements and the main results achieved.

In the four Calls that have taken place, MOLAB received a total of 43 proposals, of which 41 proposals were considered feasible and were evaluated by the M-PRP: 10 relative to the first deadline of 31st January 2021; 7 at the second deadline of 30th June 2021, 13 at the third deadline of 30th November 2021 and 11 proposals from the fourth 29th April 2022. Of these proposals, 4 were selected for MOLAB TNA from the first PRP selection, 3 from the second, 3 from the third and 4 from the fourth PRP selection (Appendix II).

KPI_{Demand}

number of requests/ available slots for MOLAB targeted at ≥ 1.2 at 12 months having an average of 4.3 at M27

KPI_{E01}. Yearly number of users requests MOLAB in 2021 received requests from 498 users.

KPI_{E02}. Yearly number of granted accesses MOLAB granted 10 projects comprising 34 access campaigns for providers

At the moment of writing this report, of the 10 successful projects (combined 1st to 3rd Call selected projects, the 4th Call projects will be carried out in the next period) 5 have been completely carried out (CH_MPPM, NIBOTRAP, MRSL, GRANJA and BelMOD) and have involved 17 access campaigns by MOLAB providers. 2 accesses are being carried out at the time of writing to the DIACOMM project. A further 3 projects are planned /or in phase of planning (SuBaiae: September/October 2022 involving MOLAB.gr; DIACOMM-planned for June-September 2022 involving the access to a further 5 MOLAB providers instrumentation; HFTV_ReVis -November 2022 with access to 5 providers instrumentation and EPHA possibly November 2022 with instrumentation from 5 MOLAB providers). The PYRITEDINOSAUR project, relative to the 1st Call, is still pending due to problems occurring at the CNRS facilities (MOLAB.fr) which couldn't be resolved yet despite the effort of WP4 coordinator. The 5 projects that have been executed are summarized in table 3, where the title of the project, the number of days of access, the objectives of the measurements and details of scientific outputs are subsequently reported.

KPI_{UserSupport}: 0.83

Target ≥ 0.80 at 18 months
From User satisfaction survey:
Practical information on how to apply as well as the scientific and technical advice available from the User helpdesk

KPI_{feedback} : 0.87

Target ≥ 0.80 at 12 months after first access
From User satisfaction survey:
Overall fulfillment of expectations

2.6.1 Scientific output of Executed Projects

Among the results of experiments performed by the users supported by this Grant Agreement through MOLAB, highlights of each concluded project are given, to show how essential the MOLAB movable equipment is for European research teams and projects in the cultural heritage field. Details of the user groups and researchers involved in each project are listed in the table in appendix III

1st CALL Project

Project Title: Colour changes in Munch paintings and study of the artist's painting materials (CH_MPPM)

User Group Leader: Irina Sandu (group leader)

Venue: Munch Museet, Oslo, Norway

The MOLAB Access project proposes a multi-analytical study following two lines of investigation; first on a selection of 5 paintings by Edvard Munch (1863-1944) from the Munch Museum (MUNCH) collection, and secondly on historic paint materials from the artist's studio. The selected paintings, made during 1907 – 1908, exhibit condition problems in connection to specific-coloured paints (red and blue areas). The conservation issues on the oil paintings are discolouration, poor adhesion, water sensitivity and pronounced cracks. The selected paintings are

technically distinct in Munch's oeuvre, as he would apply paint by little mixing of colours and heavy loaded brushstrokes, and paint squeezed directly from the tube. Moreover, these colour specific phenomena seems, from a preliminary survey, more frequently observed on paintings from this period onwards. This proposal is part of a larger ongoing project at MUNCH, with the overarching aim to characterise Edvard Munch's art materials and techniques, as well as and in parallel to the study of recurrent degradation phenomena on the artworks in the museum's collection. As such, results from the analyses of 20 paint tubes from different brands will serve as comparative material for the data from the paintings and add information on brand specific additives (paint formulations) and production methods. The obtained analytical results will collate with existing research on Edvard Munch's contemporaries with similar colour specific degradation phenomena, being an important study to carry out as these phenomena and problems most likely are applicable on artworks made with materials produced in this early-modern period of paint manufacture. This inter- and multidisciplinary study will mark a step forward in the way Munch's collection is investigated and will create a model of complementary and Outreach-driven research to be followed in future projects of MUNCH.

The investigation performed on 5 canvas paintings aimed to:

- ✓ Identify the inorganic phases (pigments, fillers) present in the coloured layers of each work);
- ✓ Identify the binding media in the paint, colouring materials and their eventual degradation patterns;
- ✓ Visualise and compare specific areas where colour changes were observed
- ✓ Map and identify possible materials responsible for the darkening of blue and red paints;
- ✓ Map the different degradation-deterioration patterns on each object;
- ✓ Define the correct artistic technique for each object.

After the acquisition of imaging and point analyses data, the integration of data from all providers will focus on: • completing the pigment palette identification and localization (all Providers) • visualization of the spatial localization of organic binders (lipid/wax distribution) • investigating the inorganic composition of the altered paints by XRD-mapping

1st CALL Project

Project Title: Non-destructive Identification of Bromoil, Oil and Transfer Photographs (NIBOTRAP)

User Group Leader Marta Oriola-Folch (group leader)

Venue: University of Barcelona, Facultat de Belles Arts, Barcelona

Oil processes (oil, bromoil and bromoil transfer) are closely related to the pictorialist movement. These photographic techniques were disseminated by renown authors of the time such as Dr. Pla Janini, considered one of the most representative figures of Spanish artistic photography, undisputed master of bromoil recognized worldwide. These photographs are part of numerous private and public collections in archives, museums and cultural institutions. However, there is a void around these photographic processes in terms of scientific studies and research. In addition, these photographs are frequently not properly identified nor preserved due to a general lack of knowledge about this heritage, even by the personnel who takes care of it. Although the manuals of the time describe the materials used in these processes, it is not clear what compounds actually constitute these photographs (an aspect of great relevance for their conservation) due to: variations of the author, possible residues not eliminated by the baths, by-products created during the manufacturing process and changes due to aging. The aim of this project was to perform FTIR, XRF, Raman and UV-VIS-NIR analysis in photographic oil positives to find any key identification features and to expand the

knowledge of their constituent materials. The project examined at least 21 original oil positives (1920-1970) by Dr. Pla Janini, the main exponent of Spanish pictorialism, from the Museu Marítim de Barcelona and from the family collection. A further 9 oil positives by other artists were also examined. Specifically, three areas in each artwork was examined, named areas of minimum image density whitish, greyish and in maximum density areas, black, as well as on the verso where possible. The black areas provide information on the image-forming materials whereas the measurements in white and greyish areas provide information from underlying materials. Comparison with the verso measurements will indicate if the materials are part of the photographic process or of the paper support. The oil positive processes were very relevant in pictorialism (19th and 20th C.). The results obtained are being interpreted to understand key identifying features of the three oil positive types that allow their distinction. FTIR permitted the identification of pigments (hematite, prussian blue, barite, carbon black, silicate/sulfate based materials) as supported by XRF and Raman measurements. Furthermore, the cellulose support, lipid and proteic materials could be identified. Raman also permitted information regarding silver constituents to be gathered specifically in areas of visual degrade which offered an indication of incomplete rinsing during the production processes. This project fills an existing gap enabling a more precise identification of oil positives as well as providing detailed information on their composition and its possible degradation mechanisms.

1st CALL Project

Project Title: Multi-method remote sensing of Levantine Iron Age urbanism (MRSLS)

User Group Leader Aren Maeir (group leader)

Venue: Israel National Park Site, Tell es-Safi/Gath, in central Israel

The “lower city” of Iron Age Tell es-Safi is located in central Israel. Its archaeological value is very important providing unique opportunity to reveal the urban plan of the city based on systematic excavations that uncovered various contexts including the city wall and gate, public buildings, a temple, houses, and industrial installations. Earlier remote sensing methods using magnetic gradiometry revealed, buildings, streets and other feature filling this void and revealing the plan of the city in a wider extent.

The Laboratory of Geophysical Satellite Remote Sensing and Archaeoenvironment completed the geophysical mapping in selected sections of the site in collaboration with the director of the Tell es-Safi/Gath Archaeological Project Prof. Aren M. Maeir from Bar-Ilan University. The specific collaborative work intended to use additional and complementary geophysical techniques like Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) and resistivity mapping to reveal additional data on the Iron Age lower city. The survey was concentrated in three different sections (Areas M, S, Y) of the site trying to trace the continuations of the excavated features. Soil resistivity methods made use of the Geoscan RM85 resistance meter with a Twin Probe array and a resolution of 1x05m. GPR used the 225MHz antenna from

Sensors&Software to map the subsurface along parallel transect every 0.5m and sampling interval along the line equal to 0.05m. Processing of the datasets followed a systematic workflow leading to the creation of maps depicting the distribution of high or low resistance targets and depth slices of the most significant reflectors in the surveyed sections. The preliminary results show a number of targets related to buried archaeological features enabling a more robust and comprehensive view of the urban plan of the city.

2nd CALL Project

Project Title: Historical evolution of high-quality glass pieces from the Spanish Royal Glass Factory “La Granja”(GRANJA)

User Group Leader: Teresa Palomar (group leader)

Venue: Fundación Centro Nacional del Vidrio, Real Sitio de San Ildefonso, Segovia, Spain

The “Real Fábrica de Cristales de San Ildefonso” (Spanish Royal Glass Factory, <http://www.realfabricadecristales.es/es>) was created in 1727 to provide high-quality glass pieces to the Royal Palaces. During around 300 years, glass production has evolved with the stylistic norms from each century. The most common pieces are vessels, bottles, jars, and chandeliers, decorated by gilding, enamelling, polishing, cutting, engraving, or painting. Despite the glass pieces from La Granja are renowned around the world because of their high quality; up to date, the chemical analyses on the pieces from La Granja have been occasional. The main objective of the GRANJA project is to make, for the first time, a comprehensive study of 30 glass pieces produced in the Spanish Royal Glass Factory in the 18th and 19th centuries. This study will bring new information about the production in the factory, being possible to differentiate the production from each historical epoque and to identify which raw materials were used in each time. One of the challenges of this project is the analysis of complete pieces elaborated in the Spanish Royal Glass Factory. Most Modern and Contemporary glasses are glassware pieces, and they are difficult to be analysed because they are transparent, without flat areas, and with a wide variety of chemical compositions. Additionally, they are complete pieces, so it is not possible to take samples, and the museum avoids moving these fragile objects to the laboratory to prevent risks, being necessary to accomplish the analyses in-situ in the museum. The MOLAB project offered the possibility to analyse these glasses in-situ and without damage, supporting the possibility to carry out the archaeometric analysis of these pieces. Two teams from Italy analysed the pieces with Reflection Vis Hyperspectral Imaging (400-1000 nm), Micro-Raman spectroscopy (exc 532 nm), External reflection mid/near-FT-IR, and UV-VIS-NIR reflectance. The objective was to identify the chromophores used in the enamels, the technique used to gild, and the crystalline phases that generate opacity in opaque and translucent glasses. It was not possible to analyse the non-melted particles because of their small size. The analyses were carried out without problems in the storerooms in dark to avoid the interference of

artificial light. General mappings of chromophores were done on decorated pieces. It was detected common chromophores in the enamels such as cobalt, chromium, or manganese. Cobalt was also the chromophore used to elaborate the blue glasses for bottles and beakers. Regarding the opacifiants, apatite was the most common crystal in the glass matrix; however, some pieces with calcium fluoride were also identified. Finally, the analysis of gold applied following the cold technique showed the bands of different organic materials that could be used as binders. We want to complete the study with the analysis of portable X-ray fluorescence to know the chemical composition of each piece, and with the study of the tensions in the glass that can inform us about the production process, specifically about annealing.

3rd CALL Project

Project Title: Belgian Modernists: A material technical study on James Ensor and Paul Delvaux (BelMod)

User Group Leader: Geert Van der Snickt (group leader)

Venue: The Royal Museum of Fine Arts Antwerp (KMSKA), Belgium

In the Belmod campaign the DHSPI system as supplied by MOLAB.gr (FORTH-IESL) was used to investigate the belgian modernist paintings for their structural state of condition. The large canvas paintings provided the opportunity to test a new methodology for canvas vibration isolation that was very successful. Now, with DHSPI and the envisaged new diagnostic methodology, canvas paintings can be documented in great detail for their defect topography for the first time ever.

Hence this MOLAB mission resulted not only in documentation of the Belmod paintings but also to establish and validate a new practice in coherent metrology investigation for canvas paintings.

MOLAB.it (CNR-ISPC_a) performed Low Energy XRF optimized for light elements (Na, Mg, Al), using low voltage (8KV) for the X-ray source and a controlled flow of He in the detection path. The main focus was the identification of the lacquer substrate used by Ensor in the paintings 'the temptation of saint Anthony the Great' (ENSOR3, inv. 4003, KMSKA) and 'girl with upturned nose' (ENSOR1, inv. 2077, KMSKA). A preliminary analysis indicates a considerable Al content in the UV sensitive lacquer. Of interest was also the chemical composition of the grey-ish layer observed on the surface of the 'intrigue' (ENSOR2, inv. 1856, KMSKA). The results on the grey patina have to be analyzed with greater attention, since it is necessary to disentangle the signal of the patina from that coming from the underlying layer. At this stage it is unclear if it will be possible to accomplish. The presence of Na, Al and Si pigment in the blue pigment of this painting is instead confirmed, and these elements were also detected on the sky of the last painting analysed, 'The Pink Bows' by Delvaux (TPB, inv. 2850, KMSKA). In this last painting, also three spots on the foremost bow were sampled, showing considerable Al content in the two darker shades spots and

larger Pb in the lightest spot sampled. The analysis is generally complicated by the universal presence of the M lines of lead, which dominate the spectra of the grey patina spots sampled.

The painting was entirely study by NIR hyperspectral imaging by MOLAB.fr. Ten scans were needed to image the painting. The images are combine all together then are spatially and spectrally resize in order to perform further data analysis, which are still on going. Calibrations of the reflectance-spectral images and data analysis were performed using ENVI software (Harris Corporation, USA). The aim was to confirm or disprove the presence of underdrawings.

"The Pink Bows", by Paul Delvaux. 18 spots for OCT examination was chosen together with the user mostly in the central part and at signature. Up to 3 layers of varnish were detected, so signs of tampering with a signature. A preliminary version of the report was sent to the user, the final one (with conclusions) is under preparation.

Table 4 - Summary of executed projects M18-27

Access granted by each MOLAB facility (N. Days)	Project ID/Acronym/Title/USERS's leader	Discipline + Objectives	Short description of work
MOLAB.it CNR-SCITEC: 6 days UNIPG: 6 days CNR-INO: 6 days CNR-ISPC _a :5 days MOLAB. fr MNHN: 5 days	Mol_12 CH_MPPM Colour changes in Munch paintings and study of the artist's painting materials Irina Sandu (Munch Museet, Oslo, Norway)	Chemistry; humanities; material science - The study of 5 panel paintings by Munch 1907 – 1908, to understand the degrade phenomenon in connection to specific- coloured paints (red and blue areas	The investigation performed by MOLABs imaging UV-Vis-NIR hyperspectral and multispectral techniques and Raman, FTIR and UV- Vis (reflectance, fluorescence and time decay) methodologies, permitted for a characterization of the inorganic phases (pigments, fillers) and the binding media in the paints, colouring materials and their eventual degradation patterns. Where colour changes were observed It was possible to map by XRF and XRD and identify possible materials responsible for the darkening of blue and red paints; so that the degradation-deterioration patterns in each object could be defined.
MOLAB.it CNR-SCITEC: 5 days UNIPG: 5 days	MOL-5 NIBOTRAP Non-destructive Identification of Bromoil, Oil and Transfer Photographs Marta Oriola-Folch (University of Barcelona, Spain)	Chemistry; conservation - The examination of original oil positives (1920-1970) by Dr. Pla Janini to identify features of constituent materials and state of conservation	Measurements were collected using XRF spectroscopy, infrared spectroscopy in reflection mode, Raman spectroscopy (laser exc. 785 nm) and UV-vis-NIR spectroscopy providing for a detailed comparison of oil processes in 21 oil, bromoil and bromoil photographic transfers. Main results include identification of features related to pigments and binders expanding the knowledge of their constituent materials.

			Information was gathered as to the products of alteration and degrade.
<p>MOLAB.gr FORTH-IMS: 6 days</p>	<p>MOL_9 MRSL Multi-method remote sensing of Levantine Iron Age urbanism</p> <p>Aren Maeir Bar-Ilan University, Ramat-Gan, Israel</p>	<p>Humanities</p> <p>Aims to complement previous on site work (both excavations and remote sensing) with GPR and resistivity analyses, to enable a more robust and comprehensive view of the urban plan of the Iron Age city</p>	<p>Processing of the datasets followed a systematic workflow leading to the creation of maps depicting the distribution of high or low resistance targets and depth slices of the most significant reflectors in the surveyed sections. The preliminary results show a number of targets related to buried archaeological features enabling a more robust and comprehensive view of the urban plan of the city.</p>
<p>MOLAB.it CNR-SCITEC: 5 days</p> <p>UNIPG: 5 days</p>	<p>Mol_21 GRANJA Historical evolution of high-quality glass pieces from the Spanish Royal Glass Factory</p> <p>Teresa Palomar Fundación Centro Nacional del Vidrio, Segovia, Spain</p>	<p>Humanities, Material science</p> <p>The main objective of the GRANJA project was to effectuate a comprehensive study of 30 modern and contemporary glass pieces produced in the Spanish Royal Glass Factory in the 18th and 19th centuries</p>	<p>Glassware objects namely, vessels, bottles, jars, and chandeliers, decorated by gilding, enamelling, polishing, cutting, engraving, or painting were examined with Reflection Vis Hyperspectral Imaging (400-1000 nm), Micro-Raman spectroscopy (exc 532 nm), External reflection mid/near-FT-IR, and UV-VIS-NIR reflectance. Information was gathered regarding the identification of chromophores used in the enamels, the technique used to gild, and the crystalline phases that generate opacity in opaque and translucent glasses.</p>
<p>MOLAB.pl: 4 days</p> <p>MOLAB. fr: 2 days</p> <p>MOLAB. it CNR-SCITEC: 9 days UNIPG: 9 days CNR-ISPCa: 5 Days</p> <p>MOLAB uk: 7 days</p> <p>MOLAB.gr: FORTH IESL: 7 days</p>	<p>Mol_31 BelMod: Belgian Modernists: A material technical study on James Ensor and Paul Delvaux</p> <p>Geert Van der Snickt, University of Antwerp, Belgium</p>	<p>Chemistry; Material Sciences</p> <p>The main goals are to (1) investigate the modus operandi of the painters Delvaux and Ensor by characterizing their painting materials and (2) to get an overview of the structural condition of the paintings</p>	<p>In this work with DHSPI a new diagnostic methodology was tested. Here canvas paintings result to be documented in great detail for their defect topography. Low energy XRF focused on the lacquer layer of 2 of Ensors' paintings and the chemical composition of pigments in one of Delvaux's studied paintings. NIR hyperspectral imaging was used to investigate the presence of underdrawings and the re-laborations of such are still ongoing. By OCT instead, diverse layers of varnish could be encountered with questions regarding the Delvaux's signature raised.</p>
<p>MOLAB.fr (Week commencing 27th June 2022)</p>	<p>Mol_1 DIACOMM: Diagnostics for Conservation at Müstair Monastery</p>	<p>Humanities; material sciences</p> <p>The address the lack of understanding of the wall</p>	<p>At the time of writing, this large MOLAB mission has started with access provided by Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry (DHSPI) and Thermography (SIRT). The</p>

MOLAB.gr (IESL) (Week commencing 27 th June 2022) MOLAB.fr (LRMH)	Patrick Cassitti, Foundation Pro Monastery of St. John, Müstair, Switzerland	painting constituents (original and not) with a multitechnical approach to support the long-term preservation of the paintings.	study focused on a limited but representative part of the painted surface: the northern wall in front of the gallery (approx. 10 m ²)As such no results are available yet and will be detailed in the next reporting period.
--	---	--	---

3. CONCLUSIONS

The MOLAB programme in the period M1-M27 has started all its activities and has been providing access since M18. Much effort has been dedicated to the effective starting and efficient implementation of the program by the integration and automation of all procedures (from call launches to proposal selection by the PRP).

The delay of MOLAB access activities on site due to Covid-19 is not expected to prohibit MOLAB in fulfilling its promised total of 67 access campaigns in IPERION HS should an extension of 6 months be given from the actual finishing date at M42 (30th Sept. 2023) to M48 (31st March 2024). It stands to reason, that the collective number of implemented MOLAB access campaigns from all the providers combined is 19; (17 of which correspond to the five completely executed projects: CH_MPPM, NIBOTRAP, GRANJA, MRSL and BelMod and 2 access campaigns are being carried out during the current time of writing to DIACOMM). It is also noted that a further 15 access campaigns belonging to 4 projects (Subaiae, DIACOMM, HFTV_ReVis and EPHA) are in advanced stages of planning /execution. **This total of 34 accesses, that is 51% of total promised MOLAB TNA is expected to be carried out by M32, November 2022**

The accesses for the 4th Call have just been selected (29th June 2022) and announced (30th June 2022) to be fully planned and carried out in the next period. It remains to be mentioned that demand for MOLAB services remains very high, actually 4 times more than the actual slots that are available for which the slots still open for the final 5th and 6th Call should be adequately filled.

To this end, MOLAB has and is obtaining relevant scientific achievements and technical goals.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX I. MOLAB Proposals received and evaluated (Calls 1-4)

WP4- MOLAB					
PROPOSALS RECEIVED AND EVALUATED DURING THE REPORTING PERIOD					
User Group Member			Project		Access Provider
Name	Home Institution, Country	n. Users per facility (total)	ID/Acronym/Title	Selected Y/N	Short name
1st Call					
Teresa Palomar	Institute of Ceramic and Glass (ICV-CSIC), Madrid, Spain	5 (15)	Mol_2 GRANJA: Historical evolution of high-quality glass pieces from the Spanish Royal Glass Factory “La Granja”	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/ISPCa/UNIPG)
Javier Pinto	University of Valladolid, Spain	5 (5)	Mol_3 UNVEILINGPINTIA: Unveiling the structure of the necropolis and defensive systems of the vaccaean city-state of Pintia	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_ISPCc)
Katerina Kreislova	SVUOM Ltd. Prague, Czech	2 (2)	Mol_4 ATMOFIX: Study of properties of weathering steel	N	MOLAB.es
Marta Oriola-Folch	University of Barcelona; Spain	4 (8)	Mol_5 NIBOTRAP: Non-destructive Identification of Bromoil, Oil and Transfer Photographs	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/UNIPG)
Nuria Miguel	Aragonese School of Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage (ESCYRA), Huesca, Spain	9 (27)	Mol_6 PYRITEDINOSAUR: OCT, 3D structure - light scanner and integrated XRD-XRF applied to conservation dinosaurs fossils with pyrite decay and evaluation of innovate method conservation.	Y	MOLAB.uk MOLAB.cy MOLAB.fr
Suzana Damiani	University of Zagreb, Academy of Fine Arts, Zagreb, Croatia	3 (6)	Mol_7 DiODuCat-M: Discovering old Dubrovnik Catherdrals- MOLAB	N	Molab.uk MOLAB.cy
Aren Maeir	Bar-Ilan University, Ramat-Gan, Israel	1 (1)	MOL_9 MRSL: Multi-method remote sensing of Levantine Iron Age urbanism	Y	MOLAB.gr (FORTH-IMS)
Panagiota Vounisiou	Eforate of Antiquites of Lassithi, Agios Nikolaos, Greece	3 (6)	Mol_10 MeByTELAC: Multimodal Examination of Byzantine Temples in Lassithi, Crete	N	MOLAB.uk MOLAB.fr
Irina Sandu	Munch Museet, Oslo, NorwaY	2 (10)	Mol_12 CH_MPPM: Colour changes in Munch paintings and study of the artist’s painting materials	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/ISPCa/INO/UNIPG) MOLAB.fr
Angelo Cammalleri	Associazione Culturale Gaetano Messineo, Petralia Soprana (PA), ITALY	4 (4)	Mol_13 Vi.S.Ma.G: Villa Santa Maria Geophysics	N	MOLAB.gr (FORTH-IMS) MOLAB.ro
2nd Call					
Patrick Cassitti	Foundation Pro Monastery of St. John, Müstair, Switzerland	3 (24)	Mol_1 DIACOMM: Diagnostics for Conservation at Müstair Monastery	Y	MOLAB.fr MOLAB.it (CNR_ISPCa/ISPCc) MOLAB.uk MOLAB.de MOLAB.gr (IESL/OF-ADC)
Teresa Palomar	Institute of Ceramic and Glass (ICV-CSIC), Madrid, Spain	3 (15)	Mol_21 GRANJA: Historical evolution of high-quality glass pieces from the Spanish Royal Glass Factory “La Granja”	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/UNIPG/ ISPCa)

Anna Vila	La Caixa Foundation, Barcelona, Spain	3 (6)	Mol_14 MIRO: Material Characterization of Large Format Miró Tapestries	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/UNIPG) MOLAB.uk
Fabio Pagano	Ministry of Cultural Heritage and Activities and Tourism (MIBACT), Pozzuoli, Naples, Italy	3 (3)	Mol_17 SuBaiae: Integrating on-land and very shallow marine geophysical investigations to detect buried archeological features in the Roman site of Baiae (Phlegrean Fields Archaeological Park, Naples, Italy).	Y	MOLAB.gr (FORTH_IMS)
Zoe Reid	National Archives of Ireland, Dublin, Ireland	3 (6)	Mol_15 RIMA: Recovering Ireland's Medieval Archives	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_INO/ISPCa)
Marc Walton	Northwestern University, Evanston, USA	3 (3)	Mol_16 SUM: The Source of Money Project: Archaeological and Archaeometric Investigations of Antas in Sardinia	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_ISPCc)
Ester S.B. Ferreira	TH Köln, Cologne, Germany	3 (3)	Mol_19 GDRPlastics: German Democratic Plastics in Design	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC)
3rd Call					
Zoe Reid	National Archives Dublin, Ireland	3 (6)	Mol_18 RIMA: Recovering Ireland's Medieval Archives	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_INO/ISPCa)
Thereza Wells	Independent, Girton, Great Britain	8 (56)	Mol_20 LEOTEXT: Leonardeshi in Context	N	MOLAB.fr MOLAB.it (CNR_ISPCa/SCITEC/INO) MOLAB.uk MOLAB.pl
Elodie Guilminot	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine, Nanates, France	19 (95)	Mol_22 EPHA: Evaluation of Protection for Heritage Aircraft	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC) MOLAB.pl MOLAB.es
Fabian Rasson	Ornament Restauratie, 4588 KA Walsoorden, Netherlands	5 (5)	Mol_23 NISSE_22: Conservation of the wall paintings in the Maria church of Nisse	N	MOLAB.gr (FORTH-IESL)
Hariclia Brecolouaki	National Hellenic Research Foundation, Athens, Greece	4 (20)	Mol_24 HFTV-ReVis: The Hunt Frieze of Tomb II at Vergina, Greece: A Novel Interdisciplinary Approach for the Scientific Investigation and Revisualization of a Painted, Masterpiece of the Classical World	Y	MOLAB.it (SCITEC, ISPCa, UNIPG) MOLAB.fr (mnhn) MOLAB.uk
Javier Pinto	University of Valladolid, Spain	5 (5)	Mol_25 UNVEILING PINTIA: Unveiling the structure of the necropolis and defensive systems of the vaccaean city-state of Pintia	N	MOLAB .it (CNR-ISPCc)
Corinna Ludovica Koch Dandolo	SM conservazione e restauro. Odogno, Switzerland	4 (28)	Mol_26 CALPIA: Non-invasive investigation of a panel painting by Callisto Piazza	N	MOLAB.it (SCITEC, ISPCa, INO, UNIPG) MOLAB.fr (LRMH) MOLAB.gr (FORTH IESL)
Boris Malin	Gothenburg Museum of Art, Sweden	6 (30)	Mol_27 REMBRANDT WORKSHOP: Rembrandt workshop or follower? An investigation into material and technique of the adoration of the magi in the collection of Gotenburg museum of Art.	N	MOLAB.it (SCITEC, ISPCa, INO, UNIPG) MOLAB.fr (mnhn)
Tim Bechthold	Die Neue Sammlung - The Design Museum, Munich, Germany	5 (5)	Mol_28 GDP.ID: German Democratic Plastics in Design	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC)
Thea Winther	Swedish National Archives, Stockholm, Sweden	8 (32)	Mol_29 MoMNopSaF: The materiality of the Medieval North – the palette of Swedish and Finnish reconstructed Manuscripts	N	MOLAB.it (SCITEC, ISPCa, UNIPG) MOLAB.fr (mnhn), MOLAB.uk

M. Antonia Zalbidea-Muñoz	polytechnic university of Valencia, Spain	6 (6)	Mol_30 DLART: Decoding Levantine Art Through a non-invasive approach.	N	MOLAB.it (CNR SCITEC), MOLAB.fr (CNRS)
Geert Van der Snickt	University of Antwerp, Belgium	10 (60)	Mol_31 BelMod: Belgian Modernists: A material technical study on James Ensor and Paul Delvaux	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR SCITEC, ISPC _a , UNIPG) MOLAB.fr (mnhn), MOLAB.uk MOLAB.gr (FORTH-IESL)
Anna Vila	La Caixa Foundation, Barcelona, Spain	2 (6)	Mol_32 MIRO TAPESTRIES: Study of Joan Miró monumental tapestries	N	MOLAB.it (CNR SCITEC, UNIPG) MOLAB.fr (mnhn)
4th Call					
Erika Smeenk-Metz	Restauratieatelier Metz/museum Boijmans van Beuningen, Netherlands	3 (9)	Mol_36 PVG: Populierenlaantje-Vincent van Gogh	N	MOLAB.it (CNR SCITEC, INO) MOLAB.pl
Katerina Kreislova	SVUOM Ltd., Czech	1 (2)	Mol_37 ATMOFIX: Study of development of protective patina layer on weathering steel modern plastics	N	MOLAB.it (CNR SCITEC) MOLAB.es
Anthi Angeli	Ephorate of Antiquities of Preveza, Greece	2 (2)	Mol_38 PANDOSIA: Landscape archaeology in Kastrì-Pandosia on the Acheron river	N	MOLAB.it (CNR ISPC _b)
Thea Winther	Swedish National Archives	9 (36)	Mol_39 MoMNopSaF: The Materiality of the Medieval North – the palette of Swedish and Finnish reconstructed Manuscripts	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR-SCITEC, ISPC _a , UNIPG) MOLAB.fr (MNHN)
Ivana Ožanić Roguljić	Institute of arhchaeology	2 (2)	Mol_40 CroDanube: Danube limes in Croatia	N	MOLAB.it (CNR-ISPC _c)
Antonina Chaban	National Institute of Optics, Italian National Research Council (CNR-INO)	8 (24)	Mol_41 Giotto@Bardi: Advanced diagnostic procedures for the informed restoration intervention on fresco wall paintings by Giotto, Bardi Chapel (Basilica Santa Croce, Florence - Italy)	Y	MOLAB.gr (FORTH-IESL) MOLAB.fr (LRMH)
Malin Borin	Gothenburg Museum of Art	7 (35)	Mol_42 REMBRANDT WORKSHOP: Rembrandt, Workshop or Follower? an investigation into material and technique of the adoration of the magi in the collection of Gothenburg Museum of Art	N	MOLAB.it (SCITEC, ISPC _a , INO, UNIPG) MOLAB.fr (MNHN)
Corinna Ludovica Koch Dandolo	Lugano Municipality - culture section	4 (28)	Mol_43 CALPIA: First in-depth scientific examinations on Callisto Piazza master's art. Research opportunity during the restoration of the "Assumption and Coronation of the Virgin" panel painting in Lugano (CH)	N	MOLAB.it (SCITEC, ISPC _a , INO, UNIPG) MOLAB.gr (FORTH-IESL) MOLAB.fr (LRMH) MOLAB.pl
Anna Chiara Giusa	The Courtauld Institute of Art	4 (20)	Mol_44 PolIME: New insights into Polidoro Caldara da Caravaggio's painting practice: the results of scientific examinations on Polidoro's southern Italian works (1527-1543) in public collections	N	MOLAB.it (SCITEC, ISPC _a , INO, UNIPG) MOLAB.uk
Nicholas Eastaugh	Dr Nicholas Eastaugh Associates Ltd	4 (28)	Mol_45 LEOTEXT: The Leonardeschi in Context	N	MOLAB.it (SCITEC, ISPC _a , INO, UNIPG) MOLAB.gr

					MOLAB.uk MOLAB.pl MOLAB.fr (LRMH)
Laura Homer	National Museum of Norway	4 (20)	Mol_47 Synthetic Varnishes: Can deteriorated synthetic varnishes be removed from sensitive modern paint films such as acrylic emulsions and polyvinyl acetates using novel cleaning methods?	Y	MOLAB.it (SCITEC, ISPC _a ,) MOLAB.gr (OF-ADC) MOLAB.uk MOLAB.pl
Miroslav Vukovic	University of Zagreb	4 (8)	Mol_48 SYFI_KARST: Systematic field survey and settlement patterns in mediterranean karst landscapes	N	MOLAB.it (CNR-ISPC _c) MOLAB.gr (FORTH-IMS)
David Thickett	English Heritage	4 (12)	Mol_49 SIM: Saving Industrial Metals	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR-ISPC _a) MOLAB.fr (CNRS) MOLAB.es

APPENDIX II. Selected Projects at MOLAB PRP Meetings (Calls 1-4)

N°	ID Project Acronym	Genre	Project Title	User Group Leader	Gender	Affiliation	Country
Selected at 1st M-PRP Meeting							
1	Mol_5 NIBOTRAP	Photographs	Non-destructive Identification of Bromoil, Oil and Transfer Photographs	M. Oriola-Folch	F	University of Barcelona	ES
2	Mol_12 CH_MPPM	Paintings	Colour changes in Munch paintings and study of the artist's painting materials	I. Sandu	F	Munch Museet	NO
3	MOL_9 MRSL	Site	Multi-method remote sensing of Levantine Iron Age urbanism	A. Maeir	M	Bar-Ilan University, Ramat-Gan	IL
4	Mol_6 PYRITEDINOSAUR	Fossils	OCT, 3D structure -light scanner and integrated XRD-XRF applied to conservation dinosaurs fossils with pyrite decay and evaluation of innovate method conservation.	N. Miguel	F	Aragonese School of Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage (ESCYRA), Huesca	ES
Selected at 2nd M-PRP Meeting							
1	Mol_17 SuBaiae	Site	Integrating on-land and very shallow marine geophysical investigations to detect buried archeological features in the Roman site of Baiae (Phlegrean Fields Archaeological Park, Naples, Italy).	F. Pagano	M	Ministry of Cultural Heritage and Activities and Tourism (MIBACT), Pozzuoli, Naples, Italy	IT
2	Mol_1 DIACOMM	Murals	Diagnostics for Conservation at Müstair Monastery	P. Cassitti	M	Foundation Pro Monastery of St. John, Müstair	CH
3	Mol_21 GRANJA	Glass objects	Historical evolution of high-quality glass pieces from the Spanish Royal Glass Factory "La Granja"	T. Palomar	F	Institute of Ceramic and Glass (ICV-CSIC), Madrid	ES
Selected at 3rd M-PRP Meeting							
1	Mol_22 EPAH	Aircraft steel	Evaluation of Protection for Heritage Aircraft	E. Guilminot	F	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine, Nanates	FR
2	Mol_24 HFTV-ReVis	Tomb site/cave	The Hunt Frieze of Tomb II at Vergina, Greece: A Novel Interdisciplinary Approach for the Scientific Investigation and Revisualization of a Painted, Masterpiece of the Classical World	H. Brecoulaki	F	National Hellenic Research Foundation, Athens	GR
3	Mol_31 BelMod	paintings	Belgian Modernists: A material technical study on James Ensor and Paul Delvaux	G. Van der Snickt	M	University of Antwerp	BE
Selected at 4th M-PRP Meeting							
1	Mol_41 Giotto@Bardi	Frescoes	Advanced diagnostic procedures for the informed restoration intervention on fresco wall paintings by Giotto, Bardi Chapel (Basilica Santa Croce, Florence - Italy)	A. Chaban	F	National Institute of Optics, Italian National Research Council (CNR-INO)	IT
2	Mol_39 MoMNopSaF	Manuscripts	The Materiality of the Medieval North – the palette of Swedish and Finnish reconstructed Manuscripts	T. Winther	F	Swedish National Archives	SE
3	Mol_49 SIM	Metals	Saving Industrial Metals	D. Thickett	M	English Heritage	GB
4	Mol_47 Synthetic Varnishes	Varnishes on modern paint	Can deteriorated synthetic varnishes be removed from sensitive modern paint film ssuch as acrylic emulsions and polyvinyl acetates using novel cleaning methods?	L. Homer	F	National Museum of Norway	NO

APPENDIX III. MOLAB Users for selected projects (Calls 1-4)

RESEARCHER				EMPLOYING ORGANIZATION/ HOME INSTITUTION			OTHER INFORMATION	
First Name	Last Name	Gender	Nationality	Name	Country	Legal status ¹	User project acronym	Activity domain ²
Marta	Oriola-Folch	Female	Spain	University of Barcelona	Spain	UNI	NIBOTRAP	Chemistry Humanities Material science
Cristina	Ruiz-Recasens	Female	Spain	University of Barcelona	Spain	UNI	NIBOTRAP	Chemistry Humanities Material science
Raquel	Freixas-Jambert	Female	Spain	University of Barcelona	Spain	UNI	NIBOTRAP	Chemistry Humanities Material science
Silvia	Dahl	Female	Spain	Museu Marítim de Barcelona	Spain	OTH	NIBOTRAP	Chemistry Humanities Material science
Irina	Sandu	Female	Romania	Munch Museet	Norway	OTH	CH_MPPM	Chemistry Humanities Material science Physics
Jin	Ferrer	Female	Norway	Munch Museet	Norway	OTH	CH_MPPM	Chemistry Humanities Material science Physics
Aren	Maeir	Male	Israel	Bar-Ilan University	Israel	UNI	MRSL	Humanities
Teresa	Palomar	Female	Spain	Institute of Ceramic and Glass (ICV-CSIC)	Spain	RES	GRANJA	Humanities Material science
Paloma	Pastor	Female	Spain	Fundación Centro Nacional del Vidrio	Spain	OTH	GRANJA	Humanities Material science
Ramos	Javier	Male	Spain	Fundación Centro Nacional del Vidrio	Spain	OTH	GRANJA	Humanities Material science
Saulo	Alvarado	Male	Spain	Fundación Centro Nacional del Vidrio	Spain	OTH	GRANJA	Humanities Material science
Concha	Juárez	Female	Spain	Fundación Centro Nacional del Vidrio	Spain	OTH	GRANJA	Humanities Material science
Geert	Van der Snickt	Male	Belgium	University of Antwerp	Belgium	UNI	BelMod	Chemistry Material science
Vandeputte	Eveline	Female	Belgium	University of Antwerp	Belgium	UNI	BelMod	Chemistry Material science
Rios-Casier	Annelies	Female	Belgium	University of Antwerp	Belgium	UNI	BelMod	Chemistry Material science
Broms	Gwen	Female	Belgium	The Royal Museum of Fine Arts Antwerp (KMSKA)	Belgium	OTH	BelMod	Chemistry Material science
Todts	Herwig	Male	Belgium	The Royal Museum of Fine Arts Antwerp (KMSKA)	Belgium	OTH	BelMod	Chemistry Material science
Gonnissen	Adriaan	Male	Belgium	The Royal Museum of Fine Arts Antwerp (KMSKA)	Belgium	OTH	BelMod	Chemistry Material science
Van Hout	Nico	Male	Belgium	The Royal Museum of Fine Arts Antwerp (KMSKA)	Belgium	OTH	BelMod	Chemistry Material science
Decq	Louise	Female	Belgium	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA)	Belgium	RES	BelMod	Chemistry Material science
Saverwyns	steven	Male	Belgium	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA)	Belgium	RES	BelMod	Chemistry Material science
Chaban	Antonina	Female	Ukraine	National Institute of Optics, Italian National	Italy	RES	Giotto@Bardi	Chemistry Humanities

				Research Council (CNR-INO)				Material Science Physics
Pintus	Renata	Female	Italy	Ministry of Culture - Opificio delle Pietre Dure	Italy	RES	Giotto@Bardi	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Physics
Lanfranchi	Maria Rosa	Female	Italy	Ministry of Culture - Opificio delle Pietre Dure	Italy	RES	Giotto@Bardi	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Physics
Penoni	Sara	Female	Italy	Ministry of Culture - Opificio delle Pietre Dure	Italy	RES	Giotto@Bardi	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Physics
Todoaro	Cristiana	Female	Italy	Ministry of Culture - Opificio delle Pietre Dure	Italy	RES	Giotto@Bardi	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Physics
Porcinai	Simone	Male	Italy	Ministry of Culture - Opificio delle Pietre Dure	Italy	RES	Giotto@Bardi	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Physics
Cagnini	Andrea	Male	Italy	Ministry of Culture - Opificio delle Pietre Dure	Italy	RES	Giotto@Bardi	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Physics
Galeotti	Monica	Female	Italy	Ministry of Culture - Opificio delle Pietre Dure	Italy	RES	Giotto@Bardi	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Physics
Winther	Thea	Female	Sweden	Swedish National Archives	Sweden	OTH	MoMNopSaF	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Norrehed	Sara	Female	Sweden	Swedish National Heritage Board	Sweden	OTH	MoMNopSaF	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Tahkokallio	Jaakko	Male	Finland	National Library of Finland	Finland	OTH	MoMNopSaF	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Heikkilä	Tuomas	Male	Finland	University of Helsinki	Finland	UNI	MoMNopSaF	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Kihlman	Erika	Female	Sweden	Stockholm University	Sweden	UNI	MoMNopSaF	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Fries Markiewicz	Johanna	Female	Sweden	Swedish National Archives	Sweden	OTH	MoMNopSaF	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Ellis Nilsson	Sara	Female	Sweden	Linnaeus University	Sweden	UNI	MoMNopSaF	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Gejrot	Claes	Male	Sweden	Swedish National Archives	Sweden	OTH	MoMNopSaF	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Strinnholm Lagergren	Karin	Female	Sweden	Linnaeus University	Sweden	UNI	MoMNopSaF	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Thickett	David	Male	United Kingdom	English Heritage	United Kingdom	PRV	SIM	Chemistry Earth Sciences & Environment
Lankester	Paul	Male	United Kingdom	English Heritage	United Kingdom	PRV	SIM	Chemistry Earth Sciences & Environment
Stanley	Bethan	Female	United Kingdom	English Heritage	United Kingdom	PRV	SIM	Chemistry Earth Sciences & Environment
Richardson	Wendy	Female	United Kingdom	English Heritage	United Kingdom	PRV	SIM	Chemistry

								Earth Sciences & Environment
Homer	Laura	Female	United Kingdom	National Museum of Norway	Norway	RES	Synthetic Varnishes	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Krogvig	Ingvild	Female	Norway	National Museum of Norway	Norway	RES	Synthetic Varnishes	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Hostland	Borre	Male	Norway	National Museum of Norway	Norway	RES	Synthetic Varnishes	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Ford	Thierry	Male	Norway	National Museum of Norway	Norway	RES	Synthetic Varnishes	Chemistry Humanities Material Science